

A Comparative Study on Individual Tax Payers preference between Old vs New Tax Regime

Ankit Goel*

Finance, IMS Ghaziabad

Parul Garg**

*Department of Management, Jiwaji University
Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India*

Abstract: In budget 2020, a new tax system has been announced and from financial year 2020-21 an individual taxpayers is having a choice to pay tax according by selecting anyone option between the new regime and existing one. This paper aims to analyze the individual taxpayer preference between the two regimes and evaluate the benefit analysis on the basis of comparison between the two systems. Primary data using convenience sampling through questionnaire method as well as secondary data from wide range of literature and journal publications have been utilized. This paper also highlights the awareness and understanding of taxpayers towards the proposed new tax regime. Thereafter this paper discusses the possible challenges and opportunities that taxpayers will face in taking the decisions regarding selection of one tax regime between two. The paper concludes with suggestions to taxpayers which help in taking the choice between the two systems so that their required objective can be achieved.

Keyword: Income Tax, New Taxation system, Budget 2020, Government, India

1. Introduction

Tax is the foremost source of income for the government at center and state level, and the development of any country's economy largely depends on the tax structure it has adopted. An easy and simple taxation structure facilitates no chance for tax evasion and along that also brings prosperity to a country's economy. In budget 2020 the finance minister of India Hon'b Nirmala Sitaraman announced a new tax system. The main feature of this new tax system is that it includes more tax slabs with lower tax rates as compared to the old Tax system. The reason behind introducing the system is that there was demand from most taxpayers from long to reduce the tax rates on existing slabs. Under new tax system there is also a catch that one cannot take the benefit of all the deductions and exemptions which is available under old Tax regime.

In general every individual want two main things from their government with regard to tax policy of the country. First thing is that the tax structure to be simplified and easy to

* Assistant Professor. ** Research Scholar.

understand to a common man and secondly the most important is that tax rates should be minimum so that their income tax liability to come down. This year too with same expectations some of the taxpayers were expecting before budget 2020 announcement that either the income tax slabs to be widened or the tax rates on existing slabs will be reduced, while some others were hoping the exemptions and deductions limits would be increased from the existing limits under various category of section 80C to 80U specially. When on 1st Feb. 2020 the Budget 2020 was proposed, it has indeed help taxpayers in one of the area that it has widened the income tax slabs with reduced tax rate on such widened income tax slabs.

In simple terms this year in Budget 2020, union finance minister introduced a new personal income tax regime for individual taxpayers. The main benefit of this new tax system is that it includes more tax slabs and that too with lower tax rates as compared to the old Tax system. Now onwards an individual is having option from financial year 2020-21 to select any one out of these two systems and pay tax accordingly. However, if one is selecting the option for such new concessional tax regime that requires the taxpayer to forego/leave certain specified deductions which is available in old tax system. Some of these deductions include standard deduction of Rs. 50,000, HRA, deduction under section 80C of Rs 1.5 lakh and interest on self-occupied property of Rs. 2 lakh which are availed by most taxpayers from last many years in old tax system. As a result, the concessional tax regime may not always be beneficial because it may not provide the same benefits of deductions and exemptions.

An individual taxpayer pays taxes on income, having a choice of two options to select either of two when filing the return from F.Y. 2020-21. With regard to select an option income tax department allows a taxpayer to shift from existing old income tax regime (availing benefits of tax exemptions and deductions) to new tax regime (lower income tax rates with no tax exemptions and deductions) or vice-versa every year as per their convenience before filing the return.

Here are the details of old tax system and new tax System with their comparison so to get better understanding of both the tax systems which are available for an individual to opt from F.Y. 2020-21.

1.1. Old Tax System: Structure

Income Tax is a Direct Tax and direct taxes are levied on taxable income earned by individuals and corporate entities, also the burden to pay and deposit these taxes is on the assessee themselves. The amount of tax applicable to you will depend on how much money you earn as income over the course of a financial year and according to the defined slab rates an individual need to pay tax to the government.

1.2. Tax Rates under Old Tax Regime

The tax calculated on the basis of tax rates under old tax regime is subject to health and education cess of 4%. Under sec. 87A a rebate is given to maximum of Rs. 12500 to those whose taxable income is upto Rs. 5,00,000 annually.

1.3. Old Tax Regime

The biggest advantage is that under old tax system when individual invest in various schemes which are tax saving schemes to save their tax, it leads to savings culture in individual and that savings also helps for any future events like marriage, education, purchase of house property, medical, etc. Also individual under old tax regime can reduce tax by taking advantages of certain exemptions allowed on various allowances and perquisites and thus reduce tax liability.

On the other hand, under the old Tax regime one has to maintain documentation and proof of investments, which may be asked in case of assessment proceedings before the tax authorities anytime and that is the reason one has to kept those for long. But under new tax regime, which may not be required.

There are many young individuals who prefer to spend than save and also senior citizens who need liquidity most of the time, they used to get stuck in old regimes as to take tax benefits they have to make investments in specified instruments, majority of which have a specific lock-in prescribed mostly of the instruments from three-five years. The tax rates are high as compared to old tax system.

1.4. New Tax System

In the budget 2020, the Finance Minister of India has announced a new tax regime for income tax. Any individual opting to be taxed under the new tax regime from FY 2020-21 onwards will have to give up certain exemptions and deduction if he or she wishes to come under this new tax system. However, the new income tax regime is optional, and individuals can either opt for the new regime or file their taxes as per the old regime.

1.5. Tax Rates under New Tax Regime: (Applicable from F.Y. 2020-21)

The tax calculated on the basis of tax rates under new tax regime is subject to health and education cess of 4%. As discussed if one opt for new tax regime with less tax rates, he or she has to forego the following deductions and exemptions:

1.6. Exemptions & Deductions Not Allowed in New Tax Regime

List of few main such deductions are as under:

(a) Clauses referred in section 10 as follows:

- 1) Leave travel concession;
- 2) House rent allowance;
- 3) (iii) Special allowance detailed in Rule 2BB (such as children education allowance, hostel allowance, transport allowance)

(b) Standard deduction, deduction for entertainment allowance and employment / professional tax as contained in Section 16;

(c) Interest under section 24 in respect of self-occupied or vacant property (loss under the head IFHP for rented house shall not be allowed to be set off under any other head

(d) Any deduction under chapter VI-A: (like section 80C, 80CCC, 80CCD, 80D, 80DD, 80DDB, 80E, 80EE, 80EEA, 80EEB, 80G, 80GG, 80GGA, 80GGC, 80IA, 80-IAB, 80-IAC, 80-IB, 80-IBA, *among others*).

1.7. New Tax Regime

Individual tax payers who are paying taxes without taking benefits or claiming exemptions and deductions under the existing system can benefit from paying a lower upfront rate of tax under the new tax regime. Under the new income tax regime the process of paying tax will be much easier for individual taxpayers as it taxpayers not have to worry about complex filings and keeping records of various investments and receipts for deductions to be claimed, hence fewer mistakes and easiness in filing.

On the other hand, taxpayers who already invest a fair amount in tax-free savings schemes like PPF, NPS and claim deductions on them will suffer if they opt for new tax regime as they will not be able to tax benefits of these exemptions and deductions. The new income tax regime can potentially lower household savings as many people will refrain from investing in tax-free schemes due to exclusion of 70 common exemptions.

This paper will highlights the benefit analysis between the two regimes by taking examples and also appraise the individual preference among two tax systems.

2. Literature Review

Bird (2010) states that tax policy trends have been decisively influenced by tax research. It focuses that if tax scholars are interested in improving policy, they should focus not on the short-term political game within which policy decisions are inevitably made in all countries but rather on the long-term game of building up institutional capacity, both within and outside governments, to articulate relevant ideas for change, to collect and analyze relevant data, and to assess and criticize the effects of such changes as are made.

Jha (2013) suggests that high dependence on indirect taxes should be reduced by raising non tax revenues and direct taxes on the super-rich. Chakrabarty (2020) discusses the difference between old and new tax system and about the various exemptions and deductions which now onwards are not available to those who will opt for new tax system. Sheth (2020) states that in the long-term, a taxpayer would indeed end up paying a higher tax amount in the new regime as compared to the old regime.

This study aims to find out the individual taxpayers preference between New vs Old Tax Regime, explore the awareness towards new tax system and examine the advantages & disadvantages of New Tax system and analyse both tax system by taking few real life examples of annual income, which help taxpayers to enable them a smooth transition between the current tax system & the new tax system.

3. Methodology

3.1. Design, Data and Data Analysis

This research study is descriptive in nature. Both the primary and secondary data collection methods were considered. The primary data was collected through a questionnaire designed for the study. Secondary data was taken from various research papers, journals, magazines, newspapers and Websites. The data and information collected is classified, tabulated and processed and its findings are presented in a systematic manner.

3.2. Sampling Plan

- **Targeted population: Individual Taxpayers**
- Sampling method: Convenience sampling
- Sample size: 80

4. Data Interpretation

4.1. Analysis from Survey

We present and interpret the results from the survey systematically in this section using Tables.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents on the basis of Gender

S.No.	Gender	No. of Respondents	Cumulative Frequency
1	Male	65	65
2	Female	15	80
	Total	80	

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Out of the total respondent's majority which accounts for 81% belong to male and rest 19% are females as is shown in Table 1.

Table2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents on the basis of Age

S.No.	Age	No. of Respondents	Cumulative Frequency
1	0 -20 Years	0	0
2	21-40 Years	42	42
3	41-60 Years	34	76
4	61 Years and Above	4	80
	Total	80	

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: In the survey undertaken, it is evident from Table 2, majority of respondents, i.e., 52% are in the age group of 21 to 40 years followed by age group of 41-60 years which accounts for about 39%. About 9% respondents are above the age of 60 years.

Table3: Frequency Distribution of Respondents on the basis of Qualification

S. No.	Qualification	No. of Respondents	Cumulative Frequency
1	Upto 12 th	3	3
2	Graduation	24	27
3	Post-Graduation	44	71
4	Others	9	80
	Total	80	

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Table 3 shows that out of the total respondents more than 55% respondents are having qualification up to post graduation. Very few which accounts for approx.3% are having qualification up to 12th class. This implies that majority respondents are educated.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Respondents on the basis of Occupation

S.No.	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Cumulative Frequency
1	Service	52	52
2	Business	19	71
3	Professionals	9	80
4	Others	0	80
	Total	80	

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Table 4 shows that 65% respondents are from the service class followed by 11% professionals including CA, lawyers etc. and nearly 23% respondents are businessman.

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Respondents on the Basis of Monthly Income

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents	Cumulative Frequency
1	Upto Rs.25000	7	7
2	Rs.25001- Rs.50000	22	29
3	Rs.50001- Rs.75000	46	75
4	Rs.75001 and above	5	80
	Total	80	

Source: Researcher’s Survey.

Interpretation: It is observed from Table 5 that around 27% respondents are having monthly income between Rs. 25001 to Rs. 50000. Only 5 respondents are having monthly income more than Rs. 75001 per month. Majority of the respondents under the study belong to income group of Rs. 50001 to Rs. 75000 p.m.

Table 6: Is your Income taxable?

S.No.	Tax on Income	No. of Respondents
1	Yes	31
2	No	49
	Total	80

Source: Researcher’s Survey.

Interpretation: Around 61% respondents are not paying tax on income but still they file return with zero income tax as is evident from Table 6.

Table 7: With whom you get your income tax return file?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Self	23
2	CA/Lawyer	42
3	Tax Return Preparers	0
	Total	65

Source: Researcher’s Survey.

Interpretation: Table 7 reveals that around 29% respondents are filing their income tax by self and more than 50% people still depend on lawyer & CA to get their return file. Around 19% respondents do not file their income tax return as their income is below taxable income.

Table 8: Do you have awareness regarding proposed changes in New Tax system introduced in Budget 2020?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Fully Aware	17
2	Aware	34
3	Neutral	6
4	Not Aware	15
5	Not Fully Aware	8

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Table 8 provides that 42% respondents are having confidence about knowledge regarding proposed changes in the new tax system. Around 29% respondents are still not aware about the changes introduced in Tax system proposed in Budget 2020.

Table 9: Which option will you select in F.Y. 2020-21 while filing your income tax return?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Old Tax System	39
2	New Tax system	17
3.	Will Decide later	24

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: We find from Table 9 that around 49% of the respondents are still believe that they will go for old system only while 21% are showing concern for switching to new tax system. 30% respondents are not yet decided and will think at the time of filing return.

Table 10: Are you satisfied with the present proposed New Tax system?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Yes	22
2	No	45
3	Can't Say	13

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Table 10 reports that more than 50% respondents are not satisfied with the new tax system & around 16% are not able to comment during the survey period.

Table 11: Do you feel that more changes are required in Indian tax system?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Yes	57
2	No	23
3	Can't Say	0

Source: Researcher's Survey.

Interpretation: Table 11 discloses that when asked about scope of further changes which can be further introduced in Indian taxation system mostly of the respondents have shown their consent for this.

If yes, in which areas (In case more than one answer, please tick multiple boxes)

Options	Yes
Less rates	12
More deductions to be allowed	53
Easiness of paying tax	0
Any other	16

Table 12: Do you feel that introduction of new tax system will help in reducing tax Evasion?

S.No.	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
1	Strongly Agree	21
2	Agree	15
3	Neutral	1
4	Disagree	17
5	Strongly Disagree	26

Source: Researcher’s Survey.

Interpretation: It is seen from Table 12 that majority of the respondents which accounts for 32% still believe that new tax system can’t help in reducing the tax evasion. At the same time 26% respondents feel that this less rates in new tax system will help to reduce tax evasion.

4.2. Comparison of Old Tax System and New Tax System

Here we have taken an example of an individual whose annual income is Rs. 6,00,000 per annum and a comparison is made that what will be the tax liability under both the regimes and where he/she can get benefited in terms of less tax liability with greater savings.

Case 1: Category - Individual, Annual Income = Rs. 6,00,000, Tax Savings = Rs. 150000 invested in PPF Account.

Interpretation: From table 13, it is seen that tax liability under old tax system is zero as one get rebate of sec. 87A compared to new tax regime where tax liability arises Rs. 23400.

Table 13: Comparison of tax liability between new vs old tax system

Income	New System (No Deductions)	Old System (with Deductions)
Annual Salary (50000 p.m.)	6,00,000	6,00,000
Less: Standard Deduction	NA	50,000
Less: Deduction u/s 80C (PPF)	NA	1,50,000
Taxable Income	6,00,000	4,00,000
Tax	23,400	No Tax
Calculation		
2.5 lac. - 5.0 lac. - 5%	12500	
5.0 lac. - 6.0 lac. - 10%	10500	
Tax	22500	
Add: Education cess	900	
Tax Payable	23,400	

Case 2: Category - Individual, Annual Income = Rs. 8,00,000, Tax Savings = Rs. 150000 invested in PPF Account.

Interpretation: From table 14, it is seen that tax liability under old tax system is zero as one get rebate of sec. 87A compared to new tax regime where tax liability arises Rs. 46800.

Table 14: Comparison of tax liability between new vs old tax system

Income	New System (No Deductions)	Old System (with Deductions)
Annual Salary (50000 p.m.)	8,00,000	8,00,000
Less: Standard Deduction	NA	50,000
Less: HRA Exemption (7000 p.m.)	NA	84,000
Less: Deduction u/s 80C (PPF)	NA	1,50,000
Less: Health Insurance 80D	NA	25,000
Taxable Income	8,00,000	4,91,000
Tax	46,800	No Tax
Calculation		
2.5 lac. - 5.0 lac. - 5%	12500	
5.0 lac. - 7.5 lac. - 10%	25000	
7.5 lac. - 8.0 lac. - 15%	7500	
Tax	45000	
Add: Education cess	1800	
Tax Payable	46,800	

Case 3: Category - Individual, Annual Income = Rs. 8,00,000, Tax Savings = Rs. 150000 invested in PPF Account, NPS = Rs. 50000, Health Ins. Premium = Rs. 25000 and Interest on home Loan= Rs. 2,00,000.

Interpretation: From table 15, it is observed that tax liability under old tax system is Rs. 18,200 only as compared to new tax regime where tax liability arises Rs. 78,000. Please note that in all the three cases discussed, taxpayer has focused on savings and invested money in various tax saving options.

Table 15: Comparison of tax liability between new vs old tax system

Income	New System (No Deductions)	Old System (with Deductions)
Annual Salary (50000 p.m.)	10,00,000	10,00,000
Less: Standard Deduction	NA	50,000
Less: Interest on Home Loan	NA	2,00,000
Less: Deduction u/s 80C (PPF)	NA	1,50,000
Less: NPS	NA	50,000
Less: Health Insurance 80D	NA	25,000
Taxable Income	10,00,000	525,000
Tax	78,000	18,200
Calculation		
2.5 lac. - 5.0 lac. - 5%	12500	12,500
5.0 lac. - 7.5 lac. - 10%	25000	5,000
7.5 lac. - 10.0 lac. - 15%	37500	
Tax	75000	17,500
Add: Education cess	3000	700
Tax Payable	78,000	18,200

4.3. Findings

In case no. 1 it can be analyzed that tax liability under old tax system is zero for income of Rs. 6,00,000 as because one get rebate of sec. 87A of the whole tax liability when it comes to the case in which taxable income is under Rs. 500000 after getting a deduction of Rs. 150000 deposited in PPF scheme (sec. 80C) compared to new tax regime where tax liability arises Rs. 23400 because one didn't get the benefit of deductions.

When tax liability is compared for individual earning annual income upto Rs. 800000 one can still reduce it to zero because of availing the benefit of deduction whereas under new tax regime a tax liability of Rs. 46800 arises. People who have annual income upto Rs. 10 Lakh, under the old tax can reduce the tax liability upto Rs. 18200 as compared to new tax system where the tax liability arises of Rs. 78000. This clearly shows that one can reduce

the tax liability to a great extent under old tax system if he/she does a saving in various tax saving instruments.

Those who don't want to invest in tax saving instruments can reduce their tax liability by switching to new tax system. Female respondents are less in the study as researcher didn't find too many female respondents who file their return by own or having awareness regarding new and old both tax systems.

Even when government has provided a facility of online portal to file income tax return, many of the taxpayers are dependent on CAs & lawyer to file their ITR. When asked about the preference among two tax systems, majority have shown their consent to select old tax system as an option instead of the new one because under old tax system it gives benefit of deductions and exemptions which ultimately reduce the tax liability to great extent and also promote saving and investments.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The taxation system in India is based on the theme that the rich should pay more tax and those who are earning less should have less burden of tax liability. To further reduce the tax liability burden government introduced the new tax system with less tax rates but a catch is there that it will not consider the deductions and is also not going to provide benefit of certain exemptions. The focus of government is here that the coming generation do not believe in much savings and hence the objective is to provide them more money to spend with less tax liability, but still the old tax system is going to be adopted by many taxpayers as it is having two sided benefits. First, it will promote the savings and investments which will help them in future and second, it will give advantage of deductions which will help further to reduce tax liability. From this year every individual has to do some homework to evaluate the tax liability burden under both regimes so to get an idea that which one is going to be a better option. Hope in the next budget 2021 government will allow some deductions to avail under the new tax system too so to give a real advantage to the taxpayers which will help the tax department to overcome the problem of tax evasion.

There is a need to improve the financial literacy regarding tax filing process among taxpayers so that individual instead of depending on CA & lawyers can do it by themselves which will further help them to understand the importance of savings and evaluate their tax liability. Tax department or the government should launch some webinar/seminar or training program to make people aware about the new tax system and the differences between the two tax systems.

New Tax system should also allow considering some deductions which will ultimately promote individuals in saving and investments which at later stage provide financial

security to the taxpayer and his/her family. Individual should evaluate their tax liability under both the tax systems, and the one which is having less tax liability should be chosen as compared to the other.

References

Bird, R., 2010, Taxation and Decentralization, World Bank Other Operational Studies, 10140, The World Bank

Chakrabarty, A. 2020 (May 15), Old vs New Income Tax Regime: At which level of income should you switch regime? Financial Express, <https://www.financialexpress.com/money/income-tax/old-vs-new-income-tax-regime-at-which-level-of-income-should-you-switch-regime/1960541/>

Jha, A., 2013, Tax Structure in India and effect on corporate, International Journal of Management and Social Sciences research, 2(10), 80-82.

Panagariya, A., 2005, India's Trade Reforms, India Policy Forum 2004, pp. 1–57. Brookings and New Delhi: National Council of Applied Economic Research.

Romer, C.D., and Romer, D.H., 2010, The Macroeconomic Effects of Tax Changes: Estimates Based on a New Measure of Fiscal Shocks, American Economic Review, 100 (3), 763-801.

Sheth, H, 2020, Budget 2021: Old vs. New Tax Regime? Here's all you need to know, BusinessLine, February 03, Mumbai.

Surana, S., 2020 (August 21), Comparison of new income tax regime with old tax regime. The Economics Times, Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/wealth/tax/comparison-of-new-income-tax-regime-with-old-tax-regime/articleshow/74504558.cms>

Xing, J., 2011, Does tax structure affect economic growth? Empirical evidence from OECD countries, Centre for Business Taxation, WP 11/20.

Zaidi, B., 2020 (June 03), New income tax slabs: Will you gain by switching to new regime? The Economics Times, Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/wealth/tax/new-income-tax-slabs-will-you-gain-by-switching-to-new-regime/articleshow/74024648.cms>